

THE ROLE OF CREATIVITY IN MASTERING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The primary definitions of creative abilities provided by international scientists are discussed in the article, along with a critical examination of the various forms of creative abilities and how they relate to thinking traits. The aim of this paper is to emphasize the importance of the students’ creativity in foreign language acquisition. Additionally, strategies for fostering creative abilities through the use of a foreign language are described.

Keywords: cognitive ability, capacity, human intelligence, risk taking, flexibility, imagination, innovative growth, interpreted, divergent.

The issue of creative personal development is more pressing now than it has ever been. Naturally, one could wonder why this component is receiving so much attention at this time. The solution is straightforward: experts who can come up with ideas and show creativity are needed in this period of active foreign technology integration into all facets of life and the execution of the digital economy agenda. The growth of creative skills enhances practical and emotional experience, shapes mental attitudes and intellectual potential, nurtures an individual's aesthetic and mental abilities, accumulates professional skills and abilities, and brings out children's innate tendencies.

The fact that all cultural values developed over centuries of history are the result of society's creative endeavors is not surprising. Furthermore, the inventiveness of the next generation will influence how far civilization may progress in the future. Being a broad education subject, learning a foreign language is a great way to help pupils develop their creative skills. Let's examine the essence and traits of a foreign language in order to comprehend its contribution to the growth of a person's creative talents. The relationship between language and creativity has been the subject of inquiry by numerous scientists. Accordingly, K. Vossler views language as a spiritual activity and a "expression of the spirit." Vossler believes that language must be studied in dynamics, throughout its production, which is predicated on ongoing innovation, in accordance with W. Humboldt's view of language as an action [Vossler,2007].

As we can see, language formation itself can already be considered an expression of an individual's creative activity. Let's start by examining the term "creativity" itself. Creative talents are part of general mental abilities and are comparable to cognitive abilities. According to E. Fromm, everyone is born with the capacity for creativity. E. Torrance clarifies that creativity is a higher thought process associated with a sudden guess that combines new associations with the problem posed. "The ability to be creative is the unity of the ability to go beyond the known and the ability to create an extensive set of associations," says S. Mednik, who also views associative thinking as one of the fundamentals for an individual's creative development. [Druzhinin, 2008].

In response to this query, Khutorskoy defines creative talents as an individual's creative traits (such as imagination, creativity, and the capacity to develop ideas) that are part of the broader notion of creativity. By examining the ways in which scientists have interpreted creative abilities in their writings, we can draw the conclusion that creative abilities are a combination of a person's unique psychophysiological traits with qualitatively novel states (e.g., changes in attitude toward surrounding events, perception of oneself and what is happening around), showing up during an activity that is novel to the person, as evidenced by its successful execution or the creation of a new product. Creativity, a steady personality attribute with a strong drive for creative endeavors, is the outcome of the process of developing creative abilities. Every person has creative qualities that emerge and grow during an activity. However, the social and educational context in which an individual lives has the biggest impact on how their creative abilities develop. It is common for psychologists to discuss the relationship between creative talents and thinking traits [Khutorskoy, 2005]. Thus, the famous American researcher J. Guilford, who studied issues of human intelligence, found that creative individuals have so-called divergent thinking. In order to consider as many choices as possible, people who exhibit this mode of thinking start looking for a way out of the situation in all directions to solve problems rather than focusing all of their efforts on finding the one right answer. These individuals frequently create links between two seemingly unrelated things or create novel combinations out of elements that are used by the majority of society in a particular way. Divergent thinking is the foundation of creative thought, and its distinguishing characteristics are: speed—the capacity to come up with and produce the most ideas in the shortest amount of time (in this instance, quantity is more important than quality); flexibility—the capacity to come up with a wide range of different ideas; originality—the capacity to come up with novel and unconventional ideas; and completeness—the capacity to polish your "product" or give it a final form [Guilford, 1965].

As for attempts to identify which specific abilities are considered creative, researcher A.N. Luk, taking into account facts from the biographies and success stories of famous extraordinary representatives of art and science, identifies 13 types of creative abilities:[Luk,1978]

1. Ability to detect a problem.
2. Towards generalization and specification.
3. To use the experience gained.
4. Towards a holistic perception of the surrounding world.
5. Towards associations.
6. To choosing one of the ways to solve the problem before checking it.
7. Towards the integration of new information into existing knowledge systems
8. To finalize the original plan.
9. Flexibility of thinking.
10. The ability of memory to produce the necessary information when required.
11. The ability to perceive things objectively, to separate what is observed from what is the result of interpretation.
12. Ease of generating ideas.
13. Creative imagination.

The classification of creative abilities presented by V.T. Kudryavtsev and V. Sinelnikov is much smaller. Scientists, relying on rich historical and cultural material, have identified 4 creative abilities formed during evolution: [Kudryavtsev,2008]

1. Realism of imagination.
2. The ability to see the whole before the parts.
3. The supra-situational-transformative nature of creative solutions.
4. Experimentation

As we can see, the only creative abilities stated here are universal personality traits. According to Altshuller, human creative potential consists of nine different components:- a strong sense of risk-taking; - divergent thinking; - flexibility in thought and action; - a high rate of thought; - the capacity to generate and express ideas that are far from banal; - a good imagination; - a high appreciation of aesthetics; - a developed intuition. The essential elements of creative abilities are identified as imagination and the capacity to make innovative choices that aim to update something that already exists or create something essentially new, according to our critical analysis of the views presented on the subject of the essence and characteristics of creative abilities. It is only via creative activities that pupils can improve their creative ability. Additionally, L.N. Tolstoy stated: "A student will only copy in life if he does not learn to create anything himself in school" [Apostolov,1995].

A foreign language education is the best way to accomplish the objectives of a student's whole personality development. It is in the process of teaching a foreign language that practicing methodologists recommend the widespread use of one of the most effective methods in modern education - project-based . Students who participate in project-based learning activities within the framework of language education not only gain and enhance the language skills they need, but they also have the chance to develop their creative thinking, autonomously plan their actions, anticipate various events, and actively engage with the linguistic reality. [Kikteva,2003]

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that a modern student of any age has creative abilities as a fundamental part of their personality. These abilities represent the union of individual psychophysiological traits of an individual with qualitatively novel states. The student has the chance to show off his creative potential and hone his creative skills during the process of learning a foreign language, which encompasses the whole development of the individual. Project activities are among the most effective tools for innovative personal growth during the foreign language learning process.

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